

Oxovanadium(IV) Complexes with Thiohydrazide Derivatives

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The complexes of oxovanadium(IV) with phenylthiohydrazide (pth), furfurylthiohydrazide (fth), *p*-anisidylthiohydrazide (*p*-anth) and salicylthiohydrazide (H_2Salth) of the formulae $VO(L)_2SO_4 \cdot nH_2O$ (where $L = pth, fth$ or *p*-anth and $n = 0$ or 1), $VO(H_2Salth)SO_4 \cdot CH_3OH$, $VO(Salth)B \cdot 3CH_3OH$ ($B = \text{pyridine}$ or β -picoline) and $VO(Salth) \cdot 4CH_3OH$ have been prepared and characterised by electronic reflectance, infrared and magnetic susceptibility measurements.

THE complexes of oxovanadium (IV) and a number of other metals with acylhydrazides and acylhydrazones have been studied in detail¹⁻⁴. Relatively a little is known about the complexes of metal ions with acylthiohydrazides⁵. Jensen and Miquel⁶ had reported that phenylthiohydrazide forms nickel (II) chelates of the same types as are formed by thiosemicarbazides⁷. Recently Dilworth *et al.*⁸ have reported a number of molybdenum (III) complexes with thiohydrazides and thiohydrazones. The complexes of oxovanadium (IV) and various other metal ions with acylthiohydrazides have not been reported hitherto. In present communication, we are reporting the complexes of oxovanadium (IV) acylthiohydrazides (L).

(R = phenyl, *p*-anisidyl, furfuryl and *o*-hydroxyphenyl groups)

Experimental

The ligands were prepared as reported in literature⁹ and vanadyl sulphate tetrahydrate and vanadyl chloride used were BDH AR grade chemicals.

Preparation of the complexes :

$VO(L)_2SO_4 \cdot nH_2O$: ($L = pth, fth$ or *p*-anth and $n = 0$ or 1).

These complexes were obtained as dark violet or dark brown precipitates when a methanolic solution of hydrated vanadyl sulphate (1.2 g in 30 ml) was treated with 1 : 2 molar proportion of appropriate ligand dissolved in minimum volume of methanol. In case of furfurylthiohydrazide, the complex was separated on adding equal volume of ether to the resulting solution of the complex. The complexes were collected on a filter, washed with methanol and ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator over $CaCl_2$.

$VO(H_2Salth)SO_4 \cdot CH_3OH$:

Hydrated vanadyl sulphate, $VOSO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$ (1.2g) was dissolved in 30-40 ml of methanol and treated with a methanolic solution salicylthiohydrazide (0.9 g, about 1 : 1 molar ratio) when a deep violet solution resulted. From the resulting solution, a dark violet complex separated out slowly. The product was collected on a filter and dried as above.

$VO(Salth)B \cdot 3CH_3OH$: ($B = \text{pyridine}$ or β -picoline).

About 1.2 g of $VOSO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$ was dissolved in 30 ml of methanol and 4-5 ml of pyridine (or β -picoline). The resulting yellowish green solution was treated with 0.9 g of ligand (about 1 : 1 molar ratio) dissolved in the same solvent. From the resulting dark violet solution, an almost black insoluble product separated out immediately. The product was collected on a filter, washed with methanol and dried in air.

$VO(Salth) \cdot 4CH_3OH$:

About 1.0 g of vanadyl chloride was dissolved in 30-40 ml of methanol and treated with the ligand in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The pH of the resulting dark violet solution was raised to 7-8 by adding methanolic solution of sodium acetate when almost black complex separated out. The product was filtered, washed and dried as above.

The elemental analyses, room temperature magnetic moment values and spectral band positions of the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

The magnetic susceptibility and electronic reflectance spectra of the complexes were recorded as reported earlier¹⁰. The IR spectra of the complexes were recorded on Perkin Elmer 577 spectrophotometer as KBr disc. The prominent IR bands are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of analytical results, the empirical formulae of the complexes are given in Table 1. Excepting salicylthiohydrazide, the other thiohydrazides appear to be bonded as bidentate neutral ligands in complexes $\text{VOL}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($L = \text{pth}$, fth or $p\text{-anth}$). Salicylthiohydrazide is bonded as a neutral molecule in complex $\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{Salth})\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ and as a dibasic acidic molecule in other complexes. Salicylthiohydrazide complexes are almost insoluble in ethanol or water but slightly dissolve in DMF. The poor solubility of the complexes indicates their polymeric nature.

The sulphato complexes $\text{VOL}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($L = \text{pth}$, fth or $p\text{-anth}$ and $n = 0$ or 1) and $\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{Salth})\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ display magnetic moment values between 1.78-1.92 BM, expected for one unpaired spin. The other oxovanadium (IV) complexes, $\text{VO}(\text{Salth})\text{B} \cdot 3\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ ($\text{B} = \text{pyridine}$ or $\beta\text{-picoline}$) and $\text{VO}(\text{Salth})4\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ show subnormal magnetic moment values (μ_{eff} 1.34–1.54 BM) similar to dinuclear oxovanadium (IV) complexes^{11,12}.

These complexes exhibit two to three medium to weak broad bands or shoulder in the region 26,000–14,000 cm^{-1} . The electronic spectral pattern of the complexes is compatible with electronic spectra of six coordinated oxovanadium (IV) complexes^{13,14}. (The spectral band positions with their assignments are shown in Table 1).

The IR spectra of the complexes display $\text{V} = \text{O}$ stretching vibration as strong band in the region 970-980 cm^{-1} (Table 2). In case of bischelated complexes, $\text{VOL}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ vibration is sharp while in other complexes, it is strong and broad indicating their di or polynuclear nature. In these vanadyl complexes, the $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ vibration occurs in the same region suggesting that dimerisation or polymerisation in the complexes does not take place through $\text{V} = \text{O}$ oxygen¹⁵.

The $\nu(\text{V} = \text{O})$ vibration is not affected in band position in pyridino/picoline complexes indicating that pyridine/picoline does not occupy $\text{V} = \text{O}$ axial position¹⁵.

Free thiohydrazides display strong and distinct NH_2 and N-H stretching vibrations in the region 3300-3100 cm^{-1} . In complexes, these bands are observed as only one broad and medium band between 3350 and 3100 cm^{-1} . The NH_2 deformation vibration of the ligand is slightly shifted to lower frequencies in almost all vanadyl complex. Thus, it is inferred that the terminal nitrogen atom of thiohydrazide group is one bonding site of ligand in the complexes¹⁶. These ligands possess potential thioamide group and therefore display characteristic thioamide bands in the region 1550-700 cm^{-1} . (The shift of thioamide bands in the complexes are shown in Table 2). The thioamide band IV due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ is shifted to lower frequency by 10-30 cm^{-1} in sulphato complexes while in

TABLE—I

Complex	Colour	% M Found (Reqd)	% N Found (Reqd)	% C Found (Reqd)	% H Found (Reqd)	% SO_4 Found (Reqd)	μ_{eff} (BM)	Spectral band position cm^{-1} (nm)	Assignments
$\text{VO}(\text{pth})_2\text{SO}_4$	Dark	10.81	12.06	36.11	3.57	20.34	1.86	17260m (580)	$b_2-e^*_\pi$ b^*_π $b_2-a^*_1 + C-T$
	brown	(10.94)	(11.99)	(35.97)	(3.45)	(20.55)		19680 sh (510)	
								23260 m (430)	
$\text{VO}(\text{fth})_2\text{SO}_4$	Dark	11.44	12.62	27.01	2.81	20.98	1.88		
	violet	(11.39)	(12.52)	(26.85)	(2.70)	(21.47)			
$\text{VO}(p\text{-anth})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dark	9.34	10.29	35.31	3.92	16.81	1.78	17540 m (570)	$b_2-e^*_\pi$ $b_2-b^*_1$ $b_2-a^*_1 + C-T$
	brown	(9.34)	(10.27)	(35.22)	(4.03)	(17.61)		19840 m (504)	
$\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{Salth})\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	Dark	13.91	7.81	26.61	3.41	26.51	1.92	15870 m (630)	$b_2-e^*_\pi$ $b_2-b^*_1$ $b_2-a^*_1 + C-T$
	violet	(14.02)	(7.71)	(26.44)	(3.30)	(26.44)		23260 m (430)	
								25380 m (395)	
$\text{VO}(\text{Salth})\text{Py} \cdot 3\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	Black	12.41	10.31	43.92	5.78	—	1.48	14080 mb (710)	$b_2-e^*_\pi$ $b_2-b^*_1$ $b_2-a^*_1 + C-T$
		(12.48)	(10.29)	(44.12)	(5.68)			17540 mb (570)	
								23800 m (420)	
$\text{VO}(\text{Salth})(\text{pic}) \cdot 3\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	Black	11.92	9.90	45.51	6.01	—	1.54	15870 m (633)	$b_2-e^*_\pi$ $b_2-b^*_1$ $b_2-a^*_1 + C-T$
		(12.06)	(9.95)	(45.49)	(5.97)			19150 m (522)	
								20400 m (490)	
								21600 m (493)	
$\text{VO}(\text{Salth})4\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	Dark violet	14.18 (11.11)	7.74 (7.75)	36.07 (36.57)	5.91 (6.14)	—	1.34		

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT IR BANDS OF LIGANDS AND VANADYL COMPLEXES

Ligand/Complex	$\nu(\text{NH}) + \nu(\text{OH})$ $+ \nu(\text{C—H})$	$\delta(\text{NH}_2)$	$\nu(\text{NH}) + \nu(\text{C=N})$ Thioamide band		$\nu(\text{V=O})$	$\nu(\text{C=S})$ Thioamide band IV	$\nu(\text{M—N})$ $+ \nu(\text{M—S})$	SO_4 bands	
			I	II				ν_3	ν_4
pth $\text{VO}(\text{pth})_2\text{SO}_4$	3220 sh	1598 s	1530 s	1375		840 s			
	3170 sb	1570 mb	1570	1345	970 s	820 w		1120	
<i>p</i> -anth $\text{VO}(\textit{p}\text{-anth})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	3248 sb	1603 vs	1530	1386 s		840 s		1070 w	
	3185 w								
H_2Salth $\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{Salth})\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	3410 sb	1600 vs	1570 m	1440 m	975 vs	830 w	435 w	1178 s	615 sp
	3200 sb						340 sh	1130	
$\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{Salth})\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	3275 sb	1605 s	1500 sb	1365		930 vs			
	3235 mb								
$\text{VO}(\text{Salth})\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	3240 sb	1605 sb	1555 w	1410 w	975 vs	905 m		1190 b	615
								1150	
$\text{VO}(\text{Salth})\text{Py} \cdot 3\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	3430 svb	1595 s	1550 m	1395 w	975 vs	700 w	460 m		
	3240 mb						330 w		
$\text{VO}(\text{Salth})\text{pic} \cdot 3\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	3430 svb	1590 s	1550 m		972 vs	705 w	465 m		
	3240 mb						430 w		
$\text{VO}(\text{Salth}) \cdot 4\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	3405 svb	1600 sb	1550 w		970 vs	705 w	462 w		
							340 w		

s=strong ; w=weak ; v=very ; sh=shoulder ; sp=sharp ; m=medium and b=broad.

neutral inner complexes, with H_2Salth , it disappears and a new weak band appears near 705 cm^{-1} . These facts support that the bonding of H_2Salth in neutral inner complexes takes place by deprotonation of thiol sulphur but in sulphato complexes, $\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{Salth})\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$, thiohydrazone coordinate through thione sulphur.

The IR spectrum of sulphato complex $\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{Salth})\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ displays splitting of ν_3 band of SO_4 group (Table 2) into three bands similar to bidentate sulphate group^{16, 17}. The ranges of splitted bands are similar to bridging sulphato group. The IR spectra of bischelated complexes, $\text{VOL}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($L=\text{pth}$ or *p*-anth and $n=0$ or 1) display splitting of ν_3 vibration in two bands (Table-2) similar to monodentate sulphato group¹⁷. The

Raman active ν_1 (SO_4) vibration has also been observed in these sulphato complexes as observed for coordinated sulphate group.

In far infrared region, the complexes display two to three medium to weak bands. These bands are tentatively assigned to M-N and M-S vibrations¹⁸.

From stoichiometry, magnetic and spectral properties, it can be inferred that the structure of $\text{VOL}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($L=\text{pth}$, fth or *p*-anth and $n=0$ or 1) is straight forward while those of $\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{Salth})\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ and $\text{VO}(\text{Salth})\text{B} \cdot 3\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ ($\text{B}=\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$, pyridine or β -picoline) are complicated. The probable structures of the complexes are shown in Figs. A & B, respectively.

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